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RELEVANCE OF THE BOYCOTT, DIVESTMENT, AND SANCTIONS MOVEMENT IN TIMES OF GENOCIDE

ABSTRACT

Since 2005, the Boycott, Divestment, Sanctions (BDS) movement has played an important role in countering the Zionist narrative, exposing the whitewashing of war crimes and human rights violations committed by Israel. BDS tactics inform, raise awareness, and contribute to the delegitimisation of the Zionist state, while also exerting pressure on complicit governments with the aim of politically isolating Israel. After twenty months of genocide in Gaza and the ongoing violations of international law in the West Bank and Jerusalem, BDS is more relevant than ever as a global movement of solidarity with the Palestinian people.

KEYWORDS

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The genocide triggered by Israel in Gaza following the Hamas attack on October 7 2023, has brought the international movement for Boycott, Divestment, and Sanctions (BDS) to the forefront. We can say that today the acronym BDS is familiar to anyone supporting the Palestinian cause. Numerous cases of boycotts and divestments against Israel have been recorded just in 2024. Even the issue of sanctions has been on the agenda, not only because some governments have applied them but also because it is constantly demanded by large sectors of civil societies and prominent figures worldwide.

In this article, we aim to reflect on the impacts of this growing movement and the critical debates arising within solidarity activism for Palestine.

THE ORIGIN OF BDS

The wave of international solidarity that swept the world in the 1970s and 1980s, contributing to the fall of the apartheid regime in South Africa, greatly inspired Palestinian organisations that, in 2005, called for the launch of a global campaign for boycotts, divestment, and sanctions against the State of Israel.

Already in 1997, the Israeli pacifist organization Gush Shalom was promoting a boycott of Israeli companies operating in the West Bank settlements and the products produced there. In the United Kingdom (UK), the Palestine Solidarity Campaign was involved in a boycott campaign against Israeli products in 2001. In 2004, the Palestinian Campaign for the Academic and Cultural Boycott of Israel (PACBI) emerged, primarily focusing on the academic and cultural fields. But it was with the call of a broad coalition of Palestinian organisations in 2005 that the BDS campaign became global and gained popularity. Many renowned artists and intellectuals immediately joined the movement, lending it credibility: film-maker Ken Loach, writers John Berger, Eduardo Galeano and Arundhati Roy, and musician Brian Eno were among the first.

This time, a structured, global movement with a strategic approach emerged, built around three main axes:

- Economic, cultural, and academic boycotts of Israeli or international companies and institutions complicit in the occupation;
- Divestment from companies and funds involved in the colonial economy, such as arms manufacturers, banks, and companies involved in the settlements;
- Sanctions against the Israeli government and state.

Over these twenty years, the BDS movement has achieved significant victories. Even a small country with limited mobilisation for human rights like Portugal had its own, such as the end of the collaboration between the Portuguese water company EPAL and its sister company from Israel, Mekorot in 2010; or in 2016, Portugal's withdrawal from the "Law Train" project, which aimed to unify police interrogation methods in partnership with Israel¹; additionally, in 2018, the cancellation of a performance by Tiago Rodrigues at the Israel Festival in Jerusalem and the public announcement of the author, then director of Teatro D. Maria, of his adherence to BDS.

Since the outbreak of the genocide in October 2023, there have

even been sanctions measures – the most difficult BDS requirement to achieve – by various governments, both central and local. In November 2023, Turkey, Chile, Colombia and Jordan recalled their ambassadors in Tel Aviv, and in 2024, Bolivia suspended diplomatic relations with Israel. For the first time in many decades, the United Nations General Assembly approved, by a large majority, sanctions against Israel in November 2024. Around the world, several governments have finally shown signs of distancing themselves from Israel's policies. Since December 2023, Malaysia has banned all ships flying the Israeli flag from using its ports. The Turkish government suspended all commercial relations with Israel in April 2024. A month later, Colombia announced the total suspension of arms purchases from Israel and, in June, prohibited the export of coal to the Zionist state. Brazil also suspended a \$200 million deal with Israel's largest arms manufacturer, Elbit Systems. Australia denied entry visas to Israeli soldiers and politicians suspected of war crimes. The Chilean government prohibited Israeli companies from participating in FIDAE 2024, an important international aerospace and military fair.

Thirty-five municipalities in the Basque Country passed motions calling for sanctions against the state of Israel and the severing of diplomatic relations. The Barcelona City Council suspended all relations with Israel until a permanent ceasefire and an end to war crimes. The Canterbury Regional Environment Council in New Zealand decided not to work with companies that have commercial ties with Israeli settlements in the occupied territories. The Oxford City Council in the UK passed a motion in March 2025 committing not to establish commercial or cooperation relations with entities complicit in human rights violations and international law, citing the International Court of Justice. In this context, dock workers' unions from all continents mobilized against shipments or the transit of arms to Israel.

Divestment cases also followed one another. Several Danish pension funds divested from companies and banks implicated in the West Bank settlements. KLP, which holds Norway's largest pension fund, withdrew a \$69 million investment from Caterpillar due to the company's involvement in human rights violations against Palestinians, particularly in the demolition of their homes. Also in Norway, the government advised companies not to engage in business that benefits the settlements. Intel, a multinational technology company deeply involved in the Israeli arms industry, eventually suspended the construction of a new factory in Israel.

We can find many more examples on the international BDS movement's website². Two of them are particularly interesting as they occurred within the European Union. Spain's ruling PSOE, along with other parties, voted in favour of suspending arms trade with Israel in the parliament in February 2024. A few months later, both the Spanish and Belgian deputy prime ministers called for the suspension of the EU-Israel Association Agreement and the imposition of a military embargo. For its part, the regional government of Wallonia in Belgium banned the transit of arms to Israel through its territory.

Although the European Union continues to *de facto* support the

¹ The 'Law Train' project was funded by the European Union and had as partners the Ministry of Justice and the Judicial Police of Portugal, the Israeli Ministry of Public Security, the Israeli National Police and Israel's Bar Ilan University. At urging of the BDS groups, Justice Minister Francisca van Dunem withdrew Portugal from the project.

² BNC, 2025: <https://bdsmovement.net/Indicators-BDS-Global-Impact-July-December-2024>.

Israeli government, after twenty months of genocide in Gaza and the continuous violations of international law in the West Bank and Jerusalem, these timid and isolated measures from some of the member states could be a sign of the beginning of a change, to which the widespread repudiation of the genocide, manifested massively in the streets, is certainly not unrelated.

THE ISRAELI COUNTER-OFFENSIVE

The success of the BDS movement, which celebrates two decades of existence this year, can be judged by the reaction of Israeli governments over the years. Coinciding with the start of the cultural and academic boycott (PACBI), Israel launched the official marketing and propaganda campaign “Brand Israel” to promote abroad an image of a country friendly to art and culture, a country that was not all war and massacres. This would divert the world’s attention from the violations of international law and war crimes that accompanied the ongoing territorial expansion. Nissim Ben-Sheetrit, head of Israeli diplomacy at the time, explained at the launch of the Brand Israel campaign in 2005: “We are seeing culture as a first-rate instrument of *hasbara* [information or propaganda], and I make no distinction between *hasbara* and culture”³.

The campaign consisted mainly of sending musicians, film-makers and other artists abroad, who signed a contract with the state beforehand in which they undertook to “promote the policy interest of the State of Israel via culture and art, including contributing to the creating a positive image for Israel”. However, this relationship was to remain secret: “The service provider will not present himself as an agent, emissary and/or representative of the Ministry [of Foreign Affairs].” The terms of the contract became public knowledge when the anti-Zionist Israeli writer Yitzhak Laor reproduced a copy of such contracts in the *Haaretz* edition of 25th July 2008.

Consequently, the budget available to clean up Israel’s image was generous and has been growing over the years. Nevertheless, the Israeli leadership’s concern was growing at the same rate as the pro-Palestinian groups joining BDS and, in October 2015, the Ministry of Strategic Affairs and Information was given the added responsibility of coordinating all the state’s activities aimed at combating the international boycott, divestment and sanctions movement. Since then, calls for financial support have been launched for the production and dissemination of “pro-Israeli”⁴ projects on the internet, with the aim of “strengthening support for identification with Israel within public opinion in cyberspace and supporting all pro-Israeli initiatives in their fight against the delegitimation and boycott of Israel”⁵.

The issue of legitimisation is indeed crucial to the survival of the state, which has lived, since its creation, on the myths created by its propaganda, whether it is the biblical right to occupy Palestine and the need for a safe haven after the Nazi holocaust, or the

‘only democracy’ in the Middle East, open to culture, tolerant of human diversity, particularly with regard to LGBTIQ+ people, and respectful of the environment. The BDS movement has undoubtedly played an important role in countering the Zionist narrative, denouncing Israel’s whitewashing of war crimes and human rights violations. This is a situation that worries both Israel and the global pro-Israeli lobby, who see it as “a moral threat, because to boycott Israel is mainly to dirty Israel”⁶. The expression *dirty* is ironic in the mouths of those who are committed to whitewashing crimes – through pinkwashing, greenwashing, sportwashing and other washes.

One of the strongest pressures Israel has exerted on governments in recent years, particularly the European Union and the United States, has been to get them to adopt laws to outlaw boycott actions against Israel. And it has succeeded in some countries.

In the United Kingdom, for example, a law was passed in 2016 banning state-funded public organisations from boycotting Israeli products. In the same year, the Canadian parliament passed a resolution penalising the boycott of Israel and the BDS movement. In May 2019, the German parliament passed a resolution defining BDS as an anti-Semitic practice. In Texas, a teacher’s employment contract was not renewed because she refused to sign a clause pledging not to get involved in BDS campaigns. France is perhaps the country where the BDS movement has been most persecuted by the political establishment. As early as 2002, the mayor of Seclin was fined 1,000 euros for calling on his municipality to boycott Israeli products in protest at the Israeli government’s policy towards the Palestinians. But it was the February 2010 circular by Justice Minister Alliot-Marie that started a real persecution of the boycott movement, under the equation between calls to boycott products from the settlements and, on the other hand, anti-Semitism and racial hatred. More than a hundred people have since been questioned by the police and more than 40 prosecuted in court for denouncing – mostly in supermarket actions – Israel’s violations of Palestinian rights and for raising consumer awareness of the boycott of Israeli products. According to legal experts Ghislain Poissonnier and Jean-Christophe Duhamel, who provide this data⁷, in none of the cases have the supermarkets filed a complaint against the activists; they have been prosecuted by the Public Prosecution Office or have been the subject of complaints from private organisations, such as the National Anti-Semitism Watch Office and the France-Israel Chamber of Commerce.

Many of these awareness-raising actions took place during major and bloody military offensives in the Gaza Strip, such as in 2009 and 2014. The activists were accused of discriminating against product suppliers because they were Israeli⁸.

As part of efforts to outlaw criticism of Israel’s colonial and apartheid regime, the IHRA, the International Holocaust Re-

3 Ben-Ami, Yuval, *Haaretz*, 2005: <https://www.haaretz.com/2005-09-20/ty-article/about-face/0000017f-f7e7-d318-aff-f7e786c70000>; <https://www.no2brandisrael.org/about-face/>

4 Defined as those who fight against the phenomenon of boycotting and delegitimising the State of Israel.

5 Ministry of Strategic Affairs and Information, https://www.gov.il/BlobFolder/generalpage/strategy/he/strategic_affairs_%D7%9E%D7%91%D7%97%D7%A0%D7%99%20%D7%AA%D7%9E%D7%99%D7%9B%D7%94%20-%20%D7%90%D7%99%D7%A8%D7%95%D7%A2%D7%99%20%D7%A9%D7%98%D7%97_FRN.pdf (quotation translated by the author)

6 Elnet, 2024: <https://elnetwork.fr/chronique/impossible-boycott-disrael>

7 Poissonnier, Ghislain, Duhamel, Jean-Christophe, *Revue des droits et libertés fondamentaux*, 2015: <https://revuedf.com/droit-penal/la-tentative-de-penalisation-des-appels-au-boycott-des-produits-israeliens-par-les-circulaires-alliot-marie-et-mercier/>

8 In a 2015 case that reached the European Court of Human Rights, it decided in June 2020 that the call to boycott products from a state in order to protest against the policy of that country was protected by freedom of expression. The French state was unanimously condemned by the judges and did not appeal the decision; but it did not annul the circular.

membrance Alliance, launched a campaign in 2015 to have a definition of antisemitism adopted internationally in which Israel is defined as a “Jewish collectivity” and anti-Zionist criticism is consequently equated with antisemitism. In this context, it is considered antisemitic “denying the Jewish people their right to self-determination, e.g. by claiming that the existence of a state of Israel is a racist endeavour” or “drawing comparisons of contemporary Israeli policy and that of the Nazis”.

So far, according to the IHRA, 45 countries, including Germany, the United Kingdom, France, Canada and several U.S. states, have already adopted this “working definition”⁹. In Portugal, the discussion only reached parliament in March 2025, with attempts of the right-wing parties PSD and Chega to get the IHRA’s censorious definition approved, on the pretext of implementing the “European Union Strategy on Combating Antisemitism and Fostering Jewish Life (2021-2030)”. These proposals were rejected by the other parties. A few days earlier, the Socialist Party had presented its motion for a resolution, avoiding any reference to an official definition of antisemitism, which was approved in the Portuguese parliament. Even before the parliamentary discussions and votes took place, the group *Judeus pela Paz e Justiça* [Jews for Peace and Justice] had sent an open letter to the newly appointed national coordinator of the EU Strategy, warning that:

“one of the central dimensions of the EU is to encourage the institutions to adopt the controversial ‘operational definition’ of antisemitism [...] which seeks to discourage or even criminalise speech that could be used to criticise Israel by classifying it as antisemitic”¹⁰.

Despite Israel’s attempts to penalise BDS and dissuade its activists, the movement continues to expand. Around the world, including in Portugal, a number of small local and student organisations are paying attention to the BDS movement and seeing boycott tactics as a way of getting involved in solidarity with the Palestinian people. The International Court of Justice’s conclusion that Israel is committing genocide against the people of Gaza, and the ICC’s issuance of arrest warrants for Netanyahu and his former Defence minister Yoav Gallant have reinforced the conviction of those who defend BDS that their actions are legitimate and that international pressure on Israel through these methods is necessary.

However, in the field of sympathy or pro-Palestinian activism, there are still sectors critical of the effectiveness or even legitimacy of BDS in isolating the state of Israel, as we will see below.

BDS UNDER DEBATE WITHIN THE PRO-PALESTINIAN MOVEMENT

Despite the advance mentioned above, not all defenders of the Palestinian cause support BDS as a way of pressurising Israel. In the opinion of Norman Finkelstein, an American academic and pro-Palestinian activist, son of Jewish Holocaust survivors, BDS

favours Israel because it allows Netanyahu to use it to regain the benevolence of international public opinion. By attributing to BDS the aim of destroying Israel, the Israeli prime minister makes it an anti-Semitic movement and thus places himself in a position of victimisation in the eyes of the world. For Finkelstein, as he took part in the discussion in the 2010s, BDS was the pretext that Israel needed, after having exhausted the Iran pretext, to support the theory of the satanic threat and victimisation¹¹. The Israeli government’s attacks on the BDS movement and its attempts to criminalise it would therefore not be the result of concern about a real danger of isolation, but just another play for Israel to continue justifying its crimes.

However, Finkelstein’s main criticism is that BDS is not consistent with its objectives, in not wanting to recognise the State of Israel within the 1949 borders. The boycott would be right for settlement products or institutions, since they are illegal, but it would be a mistake to apply it to Israeli entities inside Israel, even if they are implicated in the policies of occupation and apartheid. BDS cannot be based on international law, as it claims, says Finkelstein, and simultaneously ignore Israel’s rights, namely to self-determination and to have a state. In a debate with historian Ilan Pappé, the latter replies:

“There are no Israelis demanding self-determination; there is only a Jewish community demanding international recognition of a supremacist regime. The other notion, that of Jewish self-determination, is not recognisable in international law. Religions do not demand self-determination. So the point is this: the more we respect the equal rights of all those who live between the River Jordan and the Mediterranean, the less Jewish, Muslim or Christian the future political ensemble will be, whatever you want to call it. There’s no point hiding a Zionist position behind the veil of international law.”¹²

Noam Chomsky, also a well-known defender of Palestinian rights, is equally critical of BDS and has the issue of the 1949 borders in common with Finkelstein. In his opinion, the boycott tactic is valid for what concerns the illegal occupation in the eyes of international law – the territories occupied in 1967 – but not for Israel within its UN-recognised borders. In this sense, he considers the boycotts implemented by the Israeli organisation Gush Shalom from 1997 onwards to be right; just as he considers the divestments of U.S. multinationals involved in settlements to be right, as the Presbyterian Church did in 2014. But, according to Chomsky, we cannot boycott cultural and academic institutions, such as Tel Aviv University, because Israel discriminates against Arab citizens within its borders, and not boycott Harvard University at the same time, since human rights violations are much serious in the United States¹³.

On the other hand, according to Chomsky¹⁴, BDS would have emerged before its time, without any prior work to raise public awareness. Thus, unlike in South Africa, there would be no understanding of BDS in 2017 that would enable it to succeed, particularly in applying sanctions to Israel. The current movement

9 Combat Antisemitism Movement, The Center for the Study of Contemporary European Jewry, 2024: <https://combatantisemitism.org/wp-content/uploads/2024/09/2024-Mid-Year-IHRA-Report-09-26-2024.pdf>, p. 34.

10 Público, 23/02/2025.

11 Roth, Scott, Weiss, Philip, Mondoweiss, 2016: <https://mondoweiss.net/2016/04/norman-finkelstein-on-sanders-the-first-intifada-bds-and-ten-years-of-unemployment/>

12 New Internationalist, 2014, <https://newint.org/argument/2014/10/01/argument-israel-boycott-rights>

13 Chomsky, Noam, The Nation, 2014: <https://www.thenation.com/article/archive/israel-palestine-and-bds/>

14 Chomsky’s latest writings and interviews on this issue date from 2017. We do not know his position after the events of October 2023.

has not yet reached its “South African moment” and therefore cannot be effective.

“The road ahead leads not to South Africa, says Chomsky, but rather to an increase in the proportion of Jews in the Greater Israel that is being constructed. This is the realistic alternative to a two-state settlement. There is no reason to expect Israel to accept a Palestinian population it does not want.”¹⁵

Well, if we accept Chomsky’s reasoning, we are ignoring the fact that colonial independence has always taken place against the will of the colonisers. When France lost the war in Algeria, it was forced to take in a million settlers who left the land they considered their own, which was now independent. After the independence of the African colonies in 1975, around 500,000 “returnees” arrived in Portugal. When the historic moment arrives, Israel too will be forced to accept a free Palestine with the population that wants to stay there.

For the BDS movement, complying with international law only means accepting and applying the three fundamental rights of the Palestinian people recognised by the UN: Israel’s withdrawal to the border agreed in 1949, equal rights for Arab citizens of Israel and the right of return for Palestinians and their descendants expelled in 1948. Contradicting Chomsky and Finkelstein, we believe that it would be difficult to establish borders for the BDS targets – only the territories occupied since 1967 – when it is the State of Israel itself that has no intention of fixing its borders, considering them to be adaptable to the pace of the advance in the military occupation of the territory of Palestine.

The effectiveness of the BDS movement is also contested in some sectors of the far left, but for different reasons. The British organisation Revolutionary Communist International (RCI), for example, argues that “struggling against one’s own ruling class is a far greater contribution to the cause of Palestinian freedom than any number of consumer boycotts” and that “struggling for socialism at home is the only way to establish regimes that can support the Palestinians, and all oppressed peoples of the world, on the basis of genuine solidarity”¹⁶. Thus, the RCI evokes the case of South Africa to show how the beginning of the end of the apartheid regime in South Africa came about, not with boycotts, but with the entry into action, in the 1970s, of the black working masses, and also Indians, organised in a combative – and fiercely repressed – resistance. As the author of the text rightly says, it was this combativeness of black and brown workers that made the imperialist countries face the urgent need to negotiate with the ANC, imposing sanctions on the South African government and starting – finally, already in the 1980s – to withdraw support for the apartheid regime. Nevertheless, the title itself of the article we are considering – written in December 2023 on the pretence of the BDS campaign for Palestine – poses a false issue, or the wrong approach to the issue: *Did boycotts, divestment and sanctions overthrow the Apartheid regime?* We think this is an inappropriate approach because, in reality, the South African BDS movement did not claim such a powerful role in the fall of apartheid, nor does the current BDS movement set out to liberate

Palestine from the colonial heel. Its ambitions are far more modest: to contribute to ending the occupation of Palestine, just as the campaign of boycotts and sanctions against South Africa contributed to ending apartheid.

The French organisation Lutte Ouvrière (LO), for its part, has the slogan “one oppressor state, one oppressed people, two peoples who are victims of imperialism” and considers that:

“The policy of the imperialist powers and the Zionists has led to the transformation of the Palestinians into prisoners in their own country, but has also placed the Israeli people in the little more enviable condition of jailers”¹⁷.

Along these lines, three days after the Hamas attack and the unleashing of Israel’s brutal aggression against the people of Gaza, Lutte Ouvrière called for the unity of Palestinian and Jewish workers, arguing that “in Palestine as elsewhere, the working class and the poor masses have their own interests which are not limited to the aspiration for a national existence”¹⁸.

Nevertheless the history of colonialism reveals no significant examples of unity between the proletarians of the colonising society and those of the colonised society. Neither in South Africa did the white proletariat show solidarity with the black and Indian workers, nor did the French working class get involved in favour of Algerian independence, nor did anything similar happen with regard to the Portuguese colonies. Without disapproving of other organisations engaging in BDS activity, LO points to its negative effects on the victims of the colonial regime. For example, by cutting jobs if a company withdraws from Israel or a settlement under pressure from a campaign, the boycott would harm the workers, whether they are Palestinians or Israelis.

The same argument is defended by the Nouveau Parti Anticapitaliste-Révolutionnaires (NPA-R)¹⁹, which exemplifies the harmful impact of the boycott on employment with the case of Sodastream: the BDS campaign ended up forcing the company to close its factory based in a West Bank settlement, laying off 500 Palestinian workers “in favour of Israelis employed in the new Rahat factory”. For the NPA-R, as well as harming Palestinian workers, boycotts are ineffective because they do not stop the big capitalist groups from continuing to sell their goods through subterfuge. However, the NPA-R applauds and gives as a good example the solidarity and pro-BDS mobilisations of workers in their own countries, such as those of trade unionists in the UK outside the Israeli arms factory Elbit Systems, or those of Belgian maintenance workers who refused to transport arms to Israel. Like LO, the NPA-R attributes common interests to the working classes of both camps:

“The workers of Israel, like the workers of the world, have to face exploitation and rising prices, aggravated by the economic difficulties linked to the consequences of the war, which their bourgeoisie is making them pay for. They represent a potential force to which we must address: in the face of this situation of cost of living and redundancies, it is important to show that this

¹⁵ Chomsky, Noam, The Nation, 2014: <https://www.thenation.com/article/archive/israel-palestine-and-bds/>

¹⁶ Morken, Ben, In Defence of Marxism, 2023, <https://marxist.com/did-boycotts-divestment-and-sanctions-overthrow-the-apartheid-regime-in-south-africa.htm>

¹⁷ Editorial, Lutte ouvrière, de 19/11/2012. (quotation translated by the author)

¹⁸ Lutte ouvrière n° 236, 2023, https://www.lutte-ouvriere.org/portail/mensuel/2023-12-10-lextrême-gauche-la-question-palestinienne-et-le-hamas_728115.html (quotation translated by the author)

¹⁹ Tendency of the NPA which, in 2022, left the party to go its own way.

*war by the Zionist state is not theirs, that on the contrary it is turning against them.*²⁰

It turns out that the Israeli working classes — who have been demonstrating in recent years against the cost of living, the housing crisis and the fascisation of Israel's political regime — totally ignore in their demands the oppression of the Palestinian working class and the ongoing colonisation of Palestine.

On the other hand, from the earliest days of its foundation on Palestinian land, the State of Israel has continuously dispossessed the Arab population of all its means of existence. When land is confiscated, when natural resources are diverted, when the means of production are lacking, a Palestinian economy independent of the occupying force becomes unviable. The geographical fragmentation caused by the expansion of settlements, and all the segregating and security infrastructure that goes with it, such as checkpoints, separation walls and roads reserved for non-Palestinians, make mobility impossible, both for people and goods, which is necessary for economic activity. These same conditions make it difficult for those who have not yet been completely dispossessed to access their land, water sources and herds. As a result, today's Palestinian working class has no choice but to be unemployed or to try their luck in the Israeli construction sector or, less likely, in agriculture. These will always be poorly paid jobs, with no labour or union rights, no security and no guarantees. Much of this labour force still carries the humiliation of having to work on land that was stolen from them to dig the fields that were theirs and now belong to a settler family; or to build a new house on top of the ruins of the one that belonged to their ancestors.

CONCLUSION

The frequent parallels with South Africa are a source of encouragement for pro-Palestinian activism; they find similarities in the struggle of peoples against oppression and in the role of international solidarity, and foster hope for the denouement. To remember South Africa is to remember that regimes fall – dictatorships, apartheid and even empires – and to remember that we can fight and win.

Noam Chomsky considers that there is only one acceptable analogy between the current BDS movement and that of South Africa, which we think is indisputable: the weight of the United States' political and financial support for Israel, just as it was in South Africa until the apartheid regime began to crumble. We can also emphasise another, more general analogy, that in both cases we have the oppression of a colonial power and racial discrimination on the one hand, and resistance, struggle and emancipation on the other. But everything else is different, starting with the fundamental question of the labour force. Indeed, in apartheid South Africa, the black population was part of society, it was the indispensable labour force for the white power economy, even after being confined to the bantustans. In Palestine, on the other hand, the Israeli plan of ethnic cleansing makes the Palestinian population undesirable. Golda Meir already anticipated the outcome to be achieved when she said that "Palestinians do not exist". Israel has always sought to do without

the indigenous labour force, replacing it in the early days with Jewish immigration, then with Russian immigration in the 1990s and, especially after the Oslo agreements, by importing temporary and cheap workers, essentially Thai, Filipino and Chinese workers²¹.

The subjective conditions for an effective mass struggle from within can hardly germinate in a choice between hunger and servile labour. The most decisive factor in the fight against apartheid in South Africa was precisely the struggle of the black proletariat, supported by the popular masses, which transformed the revolts of the 1960s and 1970s into an organised workers' movement in the mines, factories and trade unions. The strikes of the 1980s and the boycotts of racist companies, especially in the car industry, brought the country to a standstill and finally shook the foundations of supremacist power. They brought down Botha's government and forced his successor to negotiate an end to apartheid with the ANC, the organisation that had until then been outlawed and considered terrorist. We can say that the Palestinian resistance to occupation and ethnic cleansing faces even more difficult conditions than those faced by black South Africans in overthrowing the apartheid regime. Those who think that boycotting Israeli companies harms the Palestinians themselves have not yet realised that the Palestinians have nothing to lose and everything to gain.

BDS tactics play a counter-propaganda role because they inform, educate and contribute to the delegitimisation of the Zionist state. They exert pressure on complicit governments; they aim to politically isolate Israel. The time for sanctions will come sooner or later. Let's remember that the UN's call in 1962 for sanctions against South Africa had no practical effect because, just as today Israel, neither the USA nor the United Kingdom, nor the other imperialist countries supporting the South African regime had an interest at that time in delegitimising South African apartheid. But they appeared later, in their own time, when these countries wanted to prevent power from falling into the hands of the black people.

It was undoubtedly the masses of Vietnamese who drove American troops out of the country and won their independence; just as it was the masses of black and Indian workers who overthrew the apartheid regime in South Africa. But the contribution of international solidarity in supporting their liberation struggles is indisputable. We believe that the self-determination and liberation of Palestine will be the work of the Palestinian people, encouraged and supported by the solidarity of the peoples of the whole world, which is manifesting itself today on the streets and through the boycott, divestment and sanctions movement ■

20 NPA Révolutionnaires, 2024: <https://npa-revolutionnaires.org/lutte-contre-les-crimes-de-letat-disrael-a-propos-de-bds/> (quotation translated by the author)

21 The Chinese government imposes the condition that Chinese labour is prohibited from working in settlements considered illegal. Vd. The Times of Israel, 2017, <https://www.timesofisrael.com/israel-signs-deal-to-bring-chinese-construction-workers-but-they-wont-work-in-west-bank/> and Helmy, Nadia, Modern Diplomacy, 2024, <https://moderndiplomacy.eu/2024/02/16/chinese-refusal-to-send-its-workers-to-israel-after-calling-the-israeli-reserve-in-the-war-against-hamas/>